

A revision of the genus *Genota* H. and A. Adams, 1853 (Gastropoda; Conoidea; Borsonidae) from West Africa

Revisión del género *Genota* H. y A. Adams, 1853 (Gastropoda; Conoidea; Borsonidae) de África Occidental

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ABSTRACT

The West African species of the genus *Genota* are reviewed and figured, concluding that only three species are valid. Their specific characters and distribution range are commented. *Genota vafra* Sykes, 1905 is considered a junior synonym of *Genota mitriformis* (Wood, 1828); *Genota marchandi* Pin, 1996 and *Genota nigeriensis* Vera-Peláez, 2004 are considered junior synonyms of *Genota nicklesi* Knudsen, 1952.

RESUMEN

Se revisan e ilustran las especies del género *Genota* de África Occidental, concluyendo que sólo existen tres especies válidas. Se comenta su distribución y caracteres específicos. Se considera que *Genota vafra* Sykes, 1905 es sinónimo de *Genota mitriformis* (Wood, 1828), y que *Genota marchandi* Pin, 1996 y *Genota nigeriensis* Vera-Peláez, 2004 son sinónimos posteriores de *Genota nicklesi* Knudsen, 1952.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Genota* H. & A. Adams, 1853 is endemic to the coast of West Africa and includes only a few species. NICKLÉS (1950: 129-130) indicated one species, *G. mitraeformis*, and one form "the var. *papalis*" for the area, whilst BERNARD (1984: 106) mentioned only one species in Gabon. GOFAS, PINTO AFONSO & BRANDÃO (1984: 134) recognized two species off the coast of Angola. PIN (1996) was the first to review the west African *Genota*, recognizing three species and one subspecies and describing a fourth species as new. After this publication it was generally accepted that his sub-

species mentioned as "*Genota mitraeformis* subsp. *papalis* Reeve" should be elevated to full species level. This was accepted by ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (2004: 223). Thereafter five species were thought to inhabit this area, which were easy to identify according to the characters described by their various authors: *Genota mitriformis* (Wood, 1828), *G. papalis* (Reeve, 1843), *G. vafra* (Sykes, 1906), *G. nicklesi* Knudsen, 1952 and *G. marchandi* Pin, 1996. However there was a sixth taxon which remained generally unknown, described by VERA-PELÁEZ (2004): *Genota nigeriensis* from Nigeria.

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During the course of our studies of the West African Conoidea Fleming, 1822 the authors examined the type of *Genota nicklesi* Knudsen, 1952. We confirm that Pin (1996) misunderstood this description, confusing it with juvenile/sub-adult and uncommon forms of specimens of *Genota papalis* (Reeve, 1843) and resulting in his redescription of the species under the name *Genota marchandi*. A similar error was repeated by VERA-PELÁEZ (2004) when he used eroded and discolored shells to describe *Genota nigeriensis*.

An extensive comparison of *Genota mitriformis* and *Genota vafra* from their entire distribution range also surprised the authors with the discovery that the two "species" are in fact morphs of the same, very variable species. Among hundreds of specimens, all kinds of intermediate forms were noted, making it impossible to define conchological borders to readily and reliably establish a separation. With this evidence we can but conclude that both taxa are indeed conspecific.

The aim of this paper is to re-evaluate the valid species and outline their characters. There are three species: *G. mitriformis* (Wood, 1828), *G. papalis* (Reeve, 1843), and *G. nicklesi*, Knudsen, 1952. Their shells and protoconchs are illustrated, we figure two of their radulae, and confirm type localities, distribution ranges and summarize our conclusions.

As this is mainly a conchological study and having present the important

changes recently made in the taxonomy of the different groups of Conoidea, the authors cannot reject the possibility of some future surprises based on analysis of sequence data, mainly of the mitochondrial genome. However, the differences stated until now were not supported by this kind of study.

Abbreviations

- MHNS Museo de Historia Natural "Luis Iglesias" University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
- MNHN Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France.
- NHMUK Natural History Museum United Kingdom, London (formerly BNMH), England.
- ZMUC Zoologisk Museum University of Copenhagen, Denmark.
- CGP collection of Giovanni Prella, Torino, Italy.
- CHD collection Henrikas Danilia, Klaepeda, Lithuania.
- CJC collection of Javier Conde, in Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain.
- CJH collection of Juan Horro, Vigo, Spain.
- CPR collection of Peter Ryall, Maria Rain, Austria.
- CSG collection of Sandro Gori, Livorno, Italy.
- sp specimen alive collected
- s shell empty
- f fragment
- j juvenile

TAXONOMIC PART

Superfamily CONOIDEA Fleming, 1822
Family BORSONIIDAE Bellardi, 1875
Genus *Genota* H. & A. Adams, 1853

Type species: *Genota mitriformis* (W. Wood, 1828) [*Murex*]. Subsequent designation by COSSMANN (1896).

H. & A. ADAMS (1853) described *Genota* as a subgenus of *Turris* with the following characters: "Shell mitriform; whorls finely cancellated; aperture

longer than wide; canal not produced; outer lip with a deep posterior sinus"; they included into it *G. mitriformis* Wood and *G. papalis* Reeve. The etymology

was based on “*Le Génot*” of ADANSON (1787), being the first recognised species of the group.

FISCHER (1883: 589) elevated this taxon to genus level and made an unjustified emendation to the name as “*Genotia*”.

Genota was traditionally placed in Turridae but after the “desintegration” of this family in recent years, it was subsequently considered to belong to the family Conidae, within the subfamily Conorbinae or Clathurellinae. Finally, after radula comparison and mitochondrial analysis, BOUCHET, KANTOR, SYSOEV & PUILLANDRE (2011) included this genus in the family Borsoniidae Belardi, 1875.

Undoubtedly, *Genota* shows a clear morphological affinity to real *Conus* from which it may be separated by its narrowly fusiform shell with high acute spire, elaborately sculptured last whorl with deep posterior sinus, and its radula exhibiting a strong, tuberculated base generally observed only in “turrids”.

Genota does not have an operculum. ADANSON (1757) mentioned its pres-

ence, describing it as close to a *Conus* one. This erroneous information was copied by TRYON (1884). VON MALTZAN (1883: 118) already noted that the only live collected specimen he examined had no operculum. We believe Adanson’s comment was only a supposition, because his type specimen is apparently dead taken, so we even doubt that he had ever examined an animal of this genus.

As mentioned, *Genota* is endemic to the West African area. RAYMOND (1906) used this name for West American species which are today considered in *Megasurcula* Casey, 1904. It is therefore easy to exclude similar species from other geographic areas which exhibit sufficient similarities to merit hypothetical synonymous speculation.

The genus *Genota* has a very wide distribution range in the circalittoral areas of mainland West Africa, found as far north as 25°N off the coast of Western Sahara and as far south as 15°S off Namibe, southern Angola. It is surprisingly absent from the off-shore islands in the Gulf of Guinea.

Genota mitriformis (W. Wood, 1828) (Figs. 1A-N, 4-F and 5A,B,E,F)

Le Génot Adanson, 1757: 145, pl. 9, fig. 35.

Murex mitriformis W. Wood, 1828: 15, pl. 5, fig. 25. [Type locality: «Ile de France»].

Pleurotoma mitraeformis, attributed to Valenciennes by Kiener, 1839 (pars): pl. 21, fig. 1).

Genota vafra Sykes, 1905: 317, pl. 17, fig. 9.

Type material: The type material of *Murex mitriformis* Wood could not be found (pers. com. Amelia MacLellan, from NHMUK). The unjustified emendation *Pleurotoma mitraeformis* should conserve the same type series (ICZN art. 33.2.3) as the original taxon. The type of *Le Génot* of Adanson (Figs. 1 H-I), used by KIENER (1840) for *Pleurotoma mitraeformis*, is in MNHN Paris (Typothèque Coll. Adanson n° Moll 22471). The type of *Genota vafra* is in NHMUK, reg. No. 1986119 (Figs. 1L-M).

Other material studied: Senegal: 3 s, St. Louis (CJC); 6 sp, Rufisque, 20 m (CPR); 6 sp, Gorée, 15-20 m (CPR); 3 s, Gorée (CJC); 10 sp, 4s, 4j, Baie de Hann, 15-20 m (CPR); 1 s, Dakar, 25 m (MHNS); 1 s, Dakar, 22 m (CJH); 1 s, Cap de Naz, 18 m (CJH); 7 sp, Casamance, 15-20 m (CPR). Guinea Bissau: 3 s, off Conakry (CPR). Sierra Leone: 7 s, 30-40 m (CHD). Ivory Coast: 7 sp, San Pedro, 60 m (CPR); 3 sp, San Pedro, 60 m (CJH); 9 sp, Grand Bassam, 40 m (CPR); 3 s, off Abidjan (CJC). Ghana: 22 sp, 215° off Miamia, 48 m (CPR); 12 sp, 212° off Miamia, 42 m (CPR); 4 sp, 2 j, Miamia (MHNS); 1 sp, Miamia, 25 m (CJH); 4 s, Cape Three Points (MHNS); 3 s, Cape Three Points (CJH); 26 j, off Princetown, 27 m (CPR); 9 sp, off Sekondi (CPR); 1 sp, Sekondi, 35 m (CJH); 17 sp, trawled off Shama (CPR). Cameroon: 4 s, Kribi, 10-15 m (CGP). Gabon: 3 sp, Isle Bainie, 5 m (CPR); 2 sp, Libreville, 25-30 m (CPR). Angola: 3 sp, Corimba, 20 m (CPR); 6 sp, Ilha Luanda, 40 mm (CPR); 3 j, Luanda, 30 m (CPR); 2 sp, Luanda, 40 m (CPR); 2 s, Luanda, 40 m (CJC); 3 sp, off Luanda, 35-45 m (CJH); 3 sp, Farol das Lagostas, 20 m (MHNS); 2 sp, Cacuaco, 15-20 m (CSG).

Description: The original description of WOOD (1828) consists simply of a poor drawing and the text “25 mitriformis – brown striated – Isle of France”. However it was enough to recognize the species and all subsequent authors accepted this identification.

KIENER (1840: 49-50) described *Pleurotoma mitraeformis* as follows, expanding a brief Latin diagnosis.

«Coquille allongée, fusiforme, ayant la spire pointue, moins longue que le dernier tour, et formée de neuf autres tours assez étroits dont la surface est partagée en deux parties inégales par un angle obtus garni d'une rangée de petits tubercules subpliciformes; la partie la plus étroite se trouve entre la suture et l'angle; elle est un peu concave et munie de stries très-fines; l'autre partie offre le plus souvent de petites côtes longitudinales qui sont la continuation des tubercules; la suture est linéaire, bordée d'un bourrelet légèrement arrondi; tout le reste de la coquille est couvert de grosses stries assez régulières, rapprochées, traversées par d'autres stries longitudinales et courbées, ce qui rend la surface granuleuse; le dernier tour est très-atténué à sa base; les tubercules de la carène s'y prolongent à peine. L'ouverture est fort étroite, allongée; la columelle est droite, arrondie, cylindrique; le bord droit est mince, tranchant, muni à sa partie supérieure d'une échancrure peu profonde et subtriangulaire. Cette coquille est d'un roussâtre clair, quelquefois le haut de la spire est d'un gris cendré.»

SYKES (1905) described his *Genota vafra* as follows: «Shell elongate, mitri-

form, spire well produced; apex acute; pale yellow, with brown bands; sculpture protoconch smooth, the next few whorls marked by spirals with few oblique longitudinals, the whorls slightly angulated in the middle; gradually these longitudinals become stronger, until on the penultimate whorl there is a row of nodules just below the suture, followed by a few spirals and another row of larger nodules below; the last whorl has, in addition to this sculpture, a number of smaller nodules arranged in regular spiral, as also arcuate longitudinal rows, these being continued to the base of the shell; whorls 10, plano-convex; aperture elongate, narrow, fairly straight, with a well-marked, wide notch below the suture”.

The protoconch (Figs. 5A, B and 5E, F) varies from slightly more than 2 ½ whorls to almost, but not reaching, 3 whorls. The first 2 ¼ of which are absolutely smooth and the remaining portion with arcuate spiral ribs which cover all the whorl with very faint traces of spiral lines, ending with four or five very close spiral ribs, after which starts the teleoconch.

Dimensions: The holotype of *Pleurotoma mitriformis* Wood is unknown; the holotype of *G. vafra* is 31.5 mm. Average adult is around 35 mm; maximum size seen by the authors 48 mm, Libreville, Gabon. ODHNER (1922) cited 53 mm, but did not figure his specimen, so perhaps could be the bigger *papalis*. BERNARD (1984) cited 49 mm.

(Right page) Figure 1. *Genota mitriformis* (W. Wood, 1828). A: shell, 44.6 mm, Sierra Leone, 40 m (CHD); B: shell, 37 mm, Miamia, Ghana, 43 m (CPR); C: shell, 44 mm, Liberia (CPR); D: shell, 35 mm, Luanda, Angola, 40 m (CPR); E: shell, 33.1 mm, Miamia, Ghana, 38 m (CPR); F: shell, 32 mm, Ghana, 37 m (CPR); G: shell, 34.8 mm, Guinea-Bissau, 30-50 m (CJH); H, I: syntype of Adanson's “le Genot”, 35.6 mm (MNHN); J, K: shells, 30.3 mm y 30.4 mm, Corimba, Luanda, Angola, 20 m (CPR); L, M: holotype of *Genota vafra* Sykes, 1905, 31.5 mm (MNHUK); N: shell, 28.7 mm, Guinea Conakry, 40 m (CHD).

(Página derecha) Figura 1. *Genota mitriformis* (W. Wood, 1828). A: concha, 44,6 mm, Sierra Leona, 40 m (CHD); B: concha, 37 mm, Miamia, Ghana, 43 m (CPR); C: concha, 44 mm, Liberia (CPR); D: concha, 35 mm, Luanda, Angola, 40 m (CPR); E: concha, 33,1 mm, Miamia, Ghana, 38 m (CPR); F: concha, 32 mm, Ghana, 37 m (CPR); G: concha, 34,8 mm, Guinea-Bissau, 30-50 m (CJH); H, I: sintipo de “le Genot” de Adanson, 35,6 mm (MNHN); J, K: conchas, 30,3 mm y 30,4 mm, Corimba, Luanda, Angola, 20 m (CPR); L, M: holotipo de *Genota vafra* Sykes, 1905, 31,5 mm (MNHUK); N: concha, 28,7 mm, Guinea Conakry, 40 m (CHD).

Animal: BOYER (1997: 33) has described the animal of *G. vafra* as «rougeatre». In our collectings it was not observed.

The radula is shown in Fig. 4-F. It agrees in all characteristics with POWELL (1966: 96, text fig. E.126), when reproducing the one done by THIELE (1929: 572), and with BOUCHET *ET AL.* (2011). It must be remarked that our radula was extracted from a specimen with typical shell features of the *vafra* morph.

The radula has some similarity with that of Conidae species, being formed by two lines of marginal very modified teeth. In the present species the number of teeth is small (about 26). The tooth (Fig. 4F) is formed by a hollow tubular structure which channels the venom. The apex has a small barb in different position to that in Conidae teeth. The waist is scarcely distinct. They are very small: LC/DR = 240 (in the terminology of ROLÁN & RAYBAUDI MASSILIA, 1994a).

Habitat: Only mentioned in NICKLÉS (1950: 129, "sand or mud-sandy bottom"). Our material is from mud, sand and hard bottoms between 15 and 100 m.

Distribution: From the area of St. Louis, north Senegal along the whole mainland of West Africa to Luanda, north Angola. Apparently absent in the islands of the Gulf of Guinea. The morph usually considered as *vafra* has been historically collected off Northern Senegal to Guinea Bissau but similar specimens have now been recorded throughout West Africa. Whilst NORDSIECK (1977) and NORDSIECK & GARCÍA-TALavera (1979) reported this species in the Canary Islands, these records are erroneous. Their descriptions and illustrations seem to agree better with *G. papalis*, which has a more northern distribution range and could have been carried by trawlers operating off the Western Sahara and Mauritania to their harbour bases in these islands. No *Genota* species appear in the most recent book on the Canary Islands (HERNÁNDEZ, ROLÁN & SWINNEN, 2011).

Remarks: This species has often been named "*mitraeformis*" and attributed to

Kiener. There is no doubt that Kiener's *mitraeformis* is the same species as Wood's *mitriformis*, because Kiener himself wrote "*Wood dans son Catalogue of shells (pl. 5, fig. 5) l'a nommé Murex mitriformis*". Kiener credited the name to Valenciennes, who certainly did not describe it, and the only connection we can find is that he used to put labels in the shells of Paris Museum for his personal use or for preparation of descriptions never done before. The earlier spelling of the name *mitriformis* is the correct one.

SYKES (1905) separated *G. vafra* from *G. mitriformis* by "its less produced spire, the conspicuous rows of granules or nodules on the last whorl, and the well-marked double row of nodules on the upper whorls".

PIN (1996) separated the species with these words "*G. vafra* clearly differs from *G. mitraeformis* by its reddish colour and finer axial and spiral ribs", - character which doesn't agree with Sykes, because finer axials and spirals origin less conspicuous granules in the intersections- as well as noting that protoconchs could "unquestionably distinguish" the two. A strange assumption as he also wrote "While not a single specimen of *G. mitraeformis*, among the hundreds we examined, had an intact protoconch...".

Recent authors also considered *mitriformis* and *vafra* as valid different species, and it seems very logical looking at the extreme morphs which are often figured under both specific names: i.e. Figs 1A and 1N.

Summarizing differences from both descriptions and from the usual concept of both morphs, the characters for separating them should be the following ones: *mitriformis*: reddish colour, longer spire with narrower shape; only one row of nodules in the middle of the whorls. While *vafra*: two rows of nodules, bigger and so less numerous granules or nodules in the last whorl and pale yellow colour.

However, the authors have concluded that (lacking DNA data) there is no real separation between these mor-

Figure 2. *Genota papalis* (Reeve, 1843). A: shell, 53.5 mm, Kayar, Senegal, 100 m (CPR); B: shell, 30.5 mm, Farol das Lagostas, Luanda, Angola, 40 m (CPR); C: shell, 42.9 mm, Elmina, Ghana, 60 m (CPR); D: shell, 48.2 mm, Cape Barbas, West Sahara, 70 m (CPR); E, F: shell, 24.5 mm, Cacuo, Luanda, 30 m (CPR); G: shell, 41.5 mm, Casamance, Senegal, 30 m (CPR); H: shell, 46.2 mm, Guinea Conakry, 35 m (CHD); I: shell, 31.8 mm, Hann Bay, Dakar, Senegal, 30 m (CPR); J: shell, 28.5 mm, Mauritania, 35 m (CPR); K: shell, 30 mm, Luanda, Angola, 40 m (CPR).

Figura 2. *Genota papalis* (Reeve, 1843). A: concha, 53,5 mm, Kayar, Senegal, 100 m (CPR); B: concha, 30,5 mm, Farol das Lagostas, Luanda, Angola, 40 m (CPR); C: shell, 42,9 mm, Elmina, Ghana, 60 m (CPR); D: concha, 48,2 mm, Cabo Barbas, Sahara occidental, 70 m (CPR); E, F: concha, 24,5 mm, Cacuo, Luanda, Angola, 30 m (CPR); G: concha, 41,5 mm, Casamance, Senegal, 30 m (CPR); H: concha, 46,2 mm, Guinea Conakry, 35 m (CHD); I: concha, 31,8 mm, Bahia de Hann, Dakar, Senegal, 30 m (CPR); J: concha, 28,5 mm, Mauritania, 35 m (CPR); K: concha, 30 mm, Luanda, Angola, 40 m (CPR).

Table I. Basic measurements for the specimens illustrated on Figure 1, ordered from lowest to highest length/width ratio. *v: type specimen of *Genota vafra*; *m: Adanson's specimen, figured by KIENER (1839) as *Genota mitraeformis*.

Table I. Mediciones de los especímenes ilustrados en la Figura 1, ordenados de menor a mayor índice longitud/anchura. *v: espécimen tipo de *Genota vafra*; *m: espécimen de Adanson, ilustrado por KIENER (1839) como *Genota mitraeformis*.

ratio length/width	ratio mouth/spire
2.75 (Fig. 1N)	1.75 (Fig. 1N)
2.91 (Fig. 1K)	
3.01 (Fig. 1L, *v)	
3.16 (Fig. 1H, *m)	1.68 (Fig. 1H, *m)
3.18 (Fig. 1J),	
3.26 (Fig. 1D)	
3.38 (Fig. 1G)	1.5 (Fig. 1F)
3.48 (Fig. 1F)	1.36 (Fig. 1G)
3.54 (Fig. 1C)	1.25 (Fig. 1C)
3.78 (Fig. 1A)	1.09 (Fig. 1B)
3.83 (Fig. 1B)	0.95 (Fig. 1A)

prospecies, because, as it is shown in the comparative plate there are enough intermediate morphs to question if those conchological characters separate them: it is possible to find shells with well-marked double row of nodules but also shells with a less marked upper row of nodules and with only a lower one, and this feature does not correspond with the size of the granules and nodules in the last whorl or with the size of the spire. In fact, when a long sample of specimens from different origins is put together, it is almost impossible to agree where the shells start with or without those characters. Even more, checking Adanson's type of *Le Génot*, it is closer to *vafra* description, because it shows the double row of nodules and more conspicuous nodules in the last whorl than usual.

The ratio length/width measured in all specimens studied goes from 2.75 (Fig. 1N) to 3.83 (Fig. 1B). At first sight it seems too much for a single species, but all kinds of intermediates measurements are found without a separation border (Table I) The same happens when measuring ratio mouth/spire, which offers a degree of variation from 0.95 (Fig. 1A) to 1.75 (Fig. 1N), with all intermediates.

It must be remarked that although usually the bigger is the first measurement the lower is the second: 3.78-0.95 (Fig. 1A) while 2.75-1.75 (Fig. 1N); it doesn't happen thus in many specimens, i.e.: 3.48-1.5 (Fig. 1F) while: 3.38-1.36 (Fig. 1G).

Regarding rows of nodules on the spire, there are shells with two clear rows of large nodules corresponding to usual morph *vafra* (Figs. 1L-N), but also some closer to usual considered *mitri-formis* (Fig. 1G), there are shells with two rows of nodules but the upper one less developed, some of them absolutely out of *vafra* concept (Figs. 1E and 1F), and there are also shells clearly into morph *vafra*, which only presents one row of nodules, showing in the upper part a subsutural cord like usual *mitri-formis* (Figs. 1J-K).

- size and number of granules in last whorl: the number of spiral bands in the body whorl, without including the little ones in the fasciole, varies from 15 to 19 in all specimens studied, and it doesn't keep a relationship with the shape of the shell (Fig. 1A has the same number that Fig. 1N). As they are crossed by axials which seems to correspond with shell growth, they always form nodules, and,

Figure 3. *Genota nicklesi* Knudsen, 1952. A, B: holotype, 32 mm (ZMUC); C, D: topotype of *Genota marchandi*, 43 mm, Casamance, Senegal, 15 m (CPR); E: holotype of *Genota marchandi*, 40.9 mm (MNHN); F, G: shell, 39.1 mm, Takoradi, Ghana, 12 m (CPR); H, I: juvenile, 21.2 mm, Cacuaco, Angola (CPR); J: shell, 47.5 mm, S. Pedro, Ivory Coast (CPR); K: shell, 41.4 mm, Vridi, Ivory Coast, 30 m (CPR); L-N: topotypes of *Genota nigeriensis*, 23.5, 19.8 and 25.8 mm, Lagos, Nigeria (CJC).
 Figura 3. *Genota nicklesi* Knudsen, 1952. A, B: holotipo, 32 mm (ZMUC); C, D: topotipo de *Genota marchandi*, 43 mm, Casamance, Senegal, 15 m (CPR); E: holotipo de *Genota marchandi*, 40,9 mm (MNHN); F, G: concha, 39,1 mm, Takoradi, Ghana, 12 m (CPR); H, I: juvenil, 21,2 mm, Cacuaco, Angola (CPR); J: concha, 47,5 mm, S. Pedro, Costa de Marfil (CPR); K: concha, 41,4 mm, Vridi, Costa de Marfil, 30 m (CPR); L-N: topotipos de *Genota nigeriensis*, 23,5, 19,8 and 25,8 mm, Lagos, Nigeria (CJC).

the less numerous the axials are, the bigger the nodules seem, but similar size of nodules can be found both in typical *vafra* morph and in *mitriformis* morph (compare Figs. 1A or 1E with the type of *vafra*).

- colour: shells vary from pale cream or pale yellow to reddish or brownish and even dark brown, usually with outer lip white or almost white and with lighter spiral bands not clearly marked in the body whorl. No real difference according to shape of the shell can be seriously stated.

Undoubtedly, although we believe that the images are clear, this opinion could be a wrong personal opinion of

the authors. However we must also consider the following more objective data:

- protoconch is absolutely impossible to be differentiated (Figs. 5A and 5F are from a typical *vafra* and Figs. 5B and 5E from a typical *mitriformis*).

- radula is identical in both morphs as already was mentioned.

- after checking shells from different places and bathymetric ranges it is also impossible to set clear habitat separation.

Thus, we believe that the only logical conclusion is to admit that they may be conspecific morphs of a very variable species.

Genota papalis (Reeve, 1843) (Figs. 2A-K and Fig. 5C)

Pleurotoma mitraeformis (unnamed variety) - Kiener, 1839: pl. 21, fig. 1a (only).

Pleurotoma papalis Reeve, 1843: pl. 4, sp. 22. [Type locality: not designate].

Genota nicklesi of AA, sensu Pin, 1996, non Knudsen, 1952.

Type material: Reeve's type, described from Stainforth's collection is supposed to be in NHMUK, but could not be found.

Other material studied: *Western Sahara*: 3 sp, 2 j, 40 m (CPR); 3 sp, Dakhla, 50-60 m (CPR); 2 s, 30-40 m (CJH). *Mauritania*: 1 sp, off Nouahdhibou, 30 m (MHNS); 1 j, 2 sp, off Nouakchott, 40-50 m (CPR). *Senegal*: 1 sp, Kayar, 100 m (CPR); 3 s, Baie de Gorée, 15 m (CPR); 6 sps, Baie de Hann, 15-20 m (CPR); 1 j, 3 sp, Casamance, 10 m (CPR); 2 sp, 2 j, Dakar (CJH); 1 sp, 1 j, Dakar (MHNS); 3 sp, Dakar (CJC). *Ivory Coast*: 1 sp, San Pedro, 60 m (CPR); 1 j, off Abidjan, 40 m (CPR). *Ghana*: 1 j, Adjua, 50 m (CPR); 2 j, 210° off Miamia Bay, 45 m (CPR); 2 sp, off Elmina, 60 m (CPR). *Angola*: 6 sp, Luanda, 40 m (CPR); 4 sp, Luanda (CJC); 3 sp, Luanda, 25-35 m (CJH); 1 j, Cacuo, 20 m (MHNS); 1 j, south Luanda, 60 m (MHNS); 2 j, Mutuco (MHNS); 5 sp, Ilha de Luanda, 50-60 m (CPR); 6 sp, Corimba, 35 m (CPR); 6 j, Corimba, 25 m (CPR).

Description: Original description (REEVE, 1843): "Shell fusiform, sharply turritid, pale yellowish brown; whorls concave round the upper part, longitudinally lightly ridged, ridges numerous, last whorl encircled with a pale band, canal short."

KIENER (1840) wrote in *Pleurotoma mitraeformis* "La variété qui est représentée dans notre pl. 21, fig. 2, est remarquable par sa forme un peu plus renflée et par une zone blanchâtre qui traverse son dernier tour".

To complete those short descriptions, we add the following: Protoconch paucispiral with slightly more than one to one and a half whorls, rounded with nucleus inclined, smooth although

showing traces of spiral lines, developing in its final part arcuate spiral ribs which cover all the whorl, well-marked transition to teleoconch, which is composed of 6/7 whorls in adult stage. It starts usually along the first two whorls with strong arcuate ribs, which by about the third whorl cover only the lower part of the whorl making it angulated in the middle, and soon turn into nodules which form a strong shoulder leaving a concave to very concave subsutural part, with a more or less marked subsutural ridge not axially sculpture and never forming nodules. In last whorl, sometimes the axial sculpture gets finer and tends to be

Figure 4. A, B: *Genota nicklesi*, shell, 17.8 mm, Kribi, Cameroon, 15 m (CGP). C-E: apex. C: *Genota nicklesi*, Casamance, Senegal, topotype of *G. marchandi* (CPR); D: *Genota nicklesi*, Lagos, Nigeria, topotype of *G. nigeriensis* (CJC); E: holotype of *Genota nicklesi* (ZMUC). F-H: radular teeth. F: *Genota mitriformis*, drawing; G, H: *Genota nicklesi*, optical photograph and drawing.
 Figura 4. A, B: *Genota nicklesi*, concha, 17,8 mm, Kribi, Camerún, 15 m (CGP). C-E: ápices. C: *Genota nicklesi*, Casamance, Senegal, topotipo de *G. marchandi* (CPR); D: *Genota nicklesi*, Lagos, Nigeria, topotipo de *G. nigeriensis* (CJC); E: holotipo de *Genota nicklesi* (ZMUC). F-H: dientes radulares. F: *Genota mitriformis*, dibujo; G, H: *Genota nicklesi*, fotografía óptica y dibujo.

attenuated, but it is always present, very strong almost as axial costae in some specimens. Spiral sculpture of homogeneous incised lines all along the complete surface of the shell, closer ones in the subsutural band including the ridge than in the lower part of the shell. They reach a number of 45 to 55 lines in the body whorl. In specimens with more marked axials, they give the shell a reticulated appearance, but never form real nodules. Aperture long and narrow, with arcuate columella, covered with parietal callus in the adult stage. Sinus U-shaped. Protoconch from white to reddish colour. Typical teleoconch colour is cream, with blotches and spots of dark brown and white usually arranged in spiral bands, with light shoulder nodules and white in all the mouth, from parietal callus to outer lip, also white in its exterior part.

Dimensions: Holotype unknown; average size around 42-45 mm; maximum size seen by the authors 53.28 mm, off Dakla, Western Sahara. ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (2004: 223) figured a specimen of 55 mm, from Guinea Bissau.

Animal: BOYER (1997: 33) described an immature specimen collected at Gorée as "plus claire et bicolore"; it was wrongly identified as *G. nicklesi*.

Habitat: This species has the deepest habitat of the *Genota* species which may account for its absence in the Niger/Congo delta areas of West Africa. After the information in MALTZAN (1883: 117), PIN (1996: 54) and BOYER (1997: 33) and our own information, the species lives between 10 and 200 m.

Distribution: The species is known from the area of Cape Barbas, Western Sahara along the mainland of West Africa to Guinea Bissau. Scarce in the Gulf of Guinea with few specimens from Ivory Coast and Ghana and so far not recorded from the Niger/Congo Deltas but appears again around Luanda, north Angola. Absent in the islands of the Gulf of Guinea. We already commented on its supposed presence in the Canary Islands.

Remarks: There are some varieties, specially in its southern distribution range, where can be found specimens with more turritid spire and slender shell, very marked sculpture or specimens with bigger nodules at the shoulder and also very marked sculpture, all of them usually uniform very light cream or light orange/brown colour (Figs 2B and 2E-F) however they agree in most features with typical shells and so these differences don't seem to have specific or even subspecific value.

We find it strange that many of the earlier authors considered *G. papalis* only a variety of *G. mitriformis*, because, apart from all other specific characters, its protoconch is absolutely different, the only paucispiral one in the genus.

It is also somewhat strange that in spite of this paucispiral protoconch, this species has such a wide geographic range, because paucispiral species usually have more restricted distribution. Due to this, we have checked shells with distant origins, and (always lacking DNA analysis) it seems clear that there are no separable geographic morphs.

The variety known as *Genota nicklesi* of AA after Pin is not a different species, but *papalis* with a different protoconch colour, finer spiral ribs and absence of nodules when crossing the axial ribs. These characters have no specific value, because it is easy to find a big degree of colour variation in the same populations, not only in the adult shell but also in the protoconch. Pin (1996) refers this supposed species to a reddish protoconch, but there are whitish, reddish and intermediate coloured protoconchs without any correspondence with the other characters of the shell, which can be more or less sculptured or smooth and have more or less fine spiral ribs without relationship with that colour. Fig. 2K illustrates a specimen with dark red protoconch showing all characters attributed to *G. papalis* by Pin, while Fig. 2J illustrates a young shell with white protoconch which agree with the ones attributed to his "*nicklesi*".

Figure 5. *Genota* protoconchs. A: *Genota mitriformis*, "morph *vafra*", lateral view; B: *Genota mitriformis*, lateral view; C: *Genota papalis*, lateral view; D: *Genota nicklesi*, lateral view; E: *Genota mitriformis*, apical view; F: *Genota mitriformis*, "morph *vafra*", apical view.

Figura 5. Protoconchas de *Genota*. A: *Genota mitriformis*, "morfo tipo *vafra*", vista lateral; B: *Genota mitriformis*, vista lateral; C: *Genota papalis*, vista lateral; D: *Genota nicklesi*, vista lateral; E: *Genota mitriformis*, vista apical; F: *Genota mitriformis*, "morfo tipo *vafra*", vista apical.

Genota nicklesi Knudsen, 1952 (Figs. 3A-N, 4A-E, 4G, 4H and 5D)

Genota nicklesi Knudsen, 1952: 176, pl. 1, fig. 12. [Type locality: 5°58'S-12°8'E, off Angola, West Africa, 26 m, mud bottom].

Genota marchandi Pin, 1996: 55, figs. 10-13. [Type locality: Senegal].

Genota nigeriensis Vera-Peláez, 2004: 99, figs. 9-14. [Type locality: Nigeria].

Genota marchadi (misspelling) - Ardovini & Cossignani, 2004: 37, fig. 222.

Type material: Holotype in ZMUC, from Atlantidae collection (Figs 3A, 3B, 4E). Holotype of *G. marchandi* is in MNHN (Fig. 3E) and one of the authors (CPR) has a shell that came from the topotype material of Pin's 31 shells (Figs. 3C, 3D, 4C) with number 14 in Pin's own handwriting. We were not allowed to study the holotype or paratypes of *nigeriensis* in the Museo Paleontológico of Estepona, Spain, but have examined the specimens in CJC, cited as "topotypes" in the description paper (five specimens, Figs. 3L-N, 4D).

Other material studied: Senegal: 1 sp, Casamance, 15 m (CPR); 1 sp, Casamance (CJH); 2 s, Dakar (CJH). Guinea-Bissau: 2 sp, 30 m (CJH). Ivory Coast: 6 sp, off San Pedro, 35-45 m (CPR); 5 sp, in Vridi Canal, Abidjan, 25-30 m (CPR). Ghana: 3 sp, Mudrachmi Bay, 30-40 m (CPR); 12 j, in front River Nyang estuary, 12-15 m (CPR); 1 s, Miamia, 18 m (CJH); 2 j, Miamia (MHNS); 8 sp, Takoradi harbour, 15-25 m (CPR); 15 sp, off Elmina, 30-50 m (CPR). Nigeria: 5 sp, off Lagos (CJC). Cameroon: 2 s, Kribi, 10-15 m (CGP). Gabon: 2 sp, 20 m (CJC). Congo: 3 sp, off Pointe Noire, 8-10 m (CPR). Angola: 27 sp, Farol das Lagostas, 20 m (CPR); 2 s, Farol das Lagostas, 20 m (CJC); 2 sps, 4 j, Farol das Lagostas, 5-20 m (MHNS); 4 sp, 12 j, Cacuo, 5-8 m (CPR); 2 s, 7 j, Cacuo, 15-20 m (MHNS); 2 sp, Cacuo, 15-20 m (CJH); 5 sp, off Luanda, 40 m (CPR); 3 j, off Luanda, 50 m (MHNS); 1 sp, Luanda, 20 m (CJC); 3 j, Luanda, 25 m (MHNS).

Description: Original description (KNUDSEN, 1952): "Shell of the typical appearance of the genus *Genota*. About 9 whorls are present. The protoconch has 3 smooth light brown whorls. On the uppermost part of the adult shell an axial sculpture of oblique ribs is seen. These whorls are distinctly shouldered. About the sixth whorl the ribs gradually become obsolete, so that the only axial sculpture is the numerous growth lines. At the same time also the shoulder tend to disappear, but can be detected as a faint rounded edge even on the body whorl. This edge forms the lower limit of the subsutural band. A spiral sculpture is seen right from the uppermost part of the adult shell, where 3 regularly incised lines are present. Further down this number gradually increases. One line near the upper suture tends to become more distinct, and two-three lines above the lower suture are more conspicuous than the lines in the middle of the whorl. The body whorl has about 25 spiral lines placed at regular intervals from below the subsutural band to the end of the siphonal canal. Aperture long and narrow, the outer lip light brown. Columella slightly concave. Outer edge

crenulated, almost straight. Sinus broad and deep, situated at some distance from the suture. Colour varies from light to darker brown, with some shells tending to orange-brown, showing always darker axial flames, and is always darker in the subsutural band, with the nodules much more lighter, when present. Interior of the aperture is uniformly brown. Holotype is 32 x 9.2 mm."

Dimensions: As mentioned in the original description holotype is 32 mm, slightly subadult. Average size larger than type, maximum size seen by the authors 48,56 mm, off Elmina, Ghana. Pin's mentions that paratype 3 of *marchandi* is 49,7 mm, but he figures six shells smaller, one of them with n° 3 written.

Specimens in Angola are generally smaller but we have seen a specimen of 45.3 mm from Cacuo (CSG).

Soft parts not recorded: The illustration by BOYER (1997: 35) under this name is erroneous as it is a specimen of *G. papalis*.

Radula: The radula has been figured under the name "*G. marchadi* Pin, 1993" in ROLÁN & RAYBAUDI MASSILIA (1994b: 20, fig. 6a). We reproduce the image here (Fig. 4G, 4H). Radular teeth with a

remote similarity to those of the *Conus* species. Relatively small (LC/DR = 90), an apical barb, and different structure seen by transparency.

Habitat: The species has been collected between 5 and 40 m, in sandy bottom.

Distribution: From the area of Casamance, south Senegal along the whole mainland of West Africa to Luanda, north Angola. Absent in the islands of the Gulf of Guinea. Well represented throughout its range.

Remarks: We must add that in many specimens axial sculpture does not become obsolete as in the type, but continues all along the whorls, although it always disappears on the subsutural band in the penultimate and last whorls, in which it is smooth or shows only spirals. The same happens with the shoulder, usually present and very often forming nodules more or less marked, although it is possible to find very smooth specimens even in juvenile stages (like Fig. 3H-I). Sinus also presents different broadness and depth.

Although KNUDSEN (1952) mentioned that the protoconch had 3 smooth whorls it was not possible to check how he counted them, because nowadays it is broken in the holotype and he described the species only upon one specimen. It doesn't reach that number in any of the specimens studied, having only 2 to 2 ¼ whorls, similar to that of *G. mitriformis* but smaller and shorter; it also develops arcuate spiral ribs covering all the whorl before the beginning of the teleoconch.

Pin's interpretation of this species, which has been and still is followed by many authors and collectors (as it is easy to confirm looking at the web for images under this name), was wrong without doubt if we compare the holotype to the shells that he figured and his description.

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Although Pin's description was not published until 1996, he made available specimens under his manuscript name some years earlier. For this reason some authors like ROLÁN & RAYBAUDI MASSILIA (1994b: 19) were able to mention the name *Genota marchandi* before the name had actually been published. It is also worth-while to remember that Pin named his species after Professor Bernard Marchand at the University of Dakar. It has often subsequently been misspelled as "*marchadi*", by some authors, e.g. ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (2004: 37, fig. 222).

VERA-PELÁEZ (2004) described as a different species *Genota nigeriensis*, indicating that the most similar was *G. nicklesi*, although, as was usual, he used the name *marchandi* for this species. As already noted, we were denied permission to borrow the type specimens but have examined the "topotypes" specimens in CJC. They are beached and discoloured shells with eroded protoconchs (as is shown in the mentioned figures and as can also be inferred from the holotype protoconch photograph published with the description), which match perfectly into the range variation of *G. nicklesi*, not so homogeneous as is written by that author. Thus, the supposed smaller size is due to subadult condition of the specimens, as the number of whorls show; the supposed differences in the protoconch are a consequence of its eroded condition, the colour seems the typical discoloured one after erosion and exposal to the sun, and other features attributed to *nicklesi* in the description paper of *nigeriensis* do not agree with many specimens, as the "wider and deeper anal sinus" or the absence of axial sculpture with prevalence of spirals in the body whorl. We show another similar dead-taken juvenile specimen from Cameroon (Figs. 4A-B) for comparison.

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